

THERMODYNAMICALLY CONSISTENT JOHNSON-COOK-LIKE MATERIAL MODEL IN COSSERAT MEDIA UNDER LARGE DEFORMATIONS FOR FUTURE MANUFACTURING SIMULATION

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Finite Element (FE) simulations of manufacturing techniques involving metals deserve proper attention when material softening occurs. It is, in fact, well known that, under these circumstances, classical Continuum Mechanics model show mesh dependency, and a regularization method is required^[1]. Among many other possible candidates, we here employ a Cosserat model to regularize the problem^[2]. The Cosserat media description introduces the micro-structure rotation as additional degree of freedom.

The hyper-elastic version of the Cosserat media is characterized by the following Helmholtz free energy:

$$\rho\psi(\#F, \#\Gamma) = \frac{\lambda}{2}(J-1)^2 + \mu\|\text{sym}(\#F - \mathbf{I})\|^2 + \mu_c\|\text{skew}(\#F - \mathbf{I})\|^2 + \frac{\beta}{2}\|\#\Gamma\|^2; \quad (1)$$

The hyper-elastic Cosserat model has been first simplified, by enhancing the media with only one rotational degree of freedom, then it has been discretized and implemented in a FE solver.

In parallel, work has been done on implementing a thermodynamically-consistent visco-plastic material model (Johnson-Cook-like) in a small deformation Cosserat theory, where the thermal variation is evaluated through a robust thermodynamic approach.

By simulating the compression of a Hat-Shaped Specimen^[3] in small deformation, it has been shown that the Cosserat theory is a possible solution to the mesh dependency problem and that the theory can simultaneously predict material viscous hardening and thermal softening.

The implementation, calibration and verification of the same material model in Large Deformation Cosserat framework will be presented at the WCCM2020. Furthermore, the characteristic lengths of the model will be identified, and the consequences of the variation of their values explored.

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